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MECHANISMS OF STATE SUPPORT FOR THE MEDICAL SERVICES MARKET

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МЕХАНИЗМЫ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ РЫНКА МЕДИЦИНСКИХ УСЛУГ

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Аннотация. Узбекистан уделяет большое внимание созданию рынка качественных медицинских услуг. Развитие рынка медицинских услуг и появление спроса и предложения на рынке услуг зависят от экономического развития страны. В последние годы рынок медицинских товаров уже сформировал определенное направление. Любой, кто активно участвует в экономике, имеет прямой доступ к услугам здравоохранения. В работе была проанализирована сфера платных медицинских услуг в стране, а также поддержки частного сектора в этой области. Установлено, что за счет привлечения иностранных специалистов в сферу частной медицины доходы, получаемые в результате трудовой деятельности, будут освобождены от подоходного налога и индивидуальных социальных выплат. Организация и управление рынком медицинских услуг в Республике Узбекистан на основе международных стандартов объясняют, что эта сфера выходит на новый уровень.

Abstract. Uzbekistan pays great attention to creating a market of high-quality medical services. The development of the medical services market and the emergence of demand and supply in the services market depend on the economic development of the country. In recent years, the medical goods market has already formed a certain direction. Anyone active in the economy has direct access to healthcare services. The work analyzed the scope of paid medical services in the country, as well as the support of the private sector in this area. It has been established that by attracting foreign specialists in the field of private medicine, the income derived from work will be exempted from income tax and individual social payments. The organization and management of the medical services market in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of international standards explains that this area is entering a new level.

Ключевые слова: медицинские услуги, качество медицинских услуг, здравоохранение, частный сектор, медицинская нужда.

Keywords: medical service, quality of medical service, healthcare, private sector, medical necessity.

At present, our country is developing new strategic economic and social reforms based on its market economy. The main purpose of our country is to improve the living standards of the people, to increase their active participation in the economy, to ensure the quality and effectiveness of life for many years. In recent years the market for goods with the development of the commodity market in our country has also defined its direction. Taking into account the fact that anyone who is

actively engaged in the economy has direct access to health services, Uzbekistan is paying a great attention to creating a market for quality medical services. The development of the market for medical services and the emergence of supply and demand in the market of services are dependent on the economic development of the country [1].

If there is an increase in the economy of the country, the greater the amount of funding for health care, the greater the quality and the size of the service. Developed legislation in Uzbekistan, which has been advancing rapidly in recent years, focuses on:

- increase the effectiveness of medical services;
- determine of additional funds for financing;
- ensure rational use of resources and provide large-scale health care services;
- identify and protect the law, duties and responsibilities of health care providers and their users;
- ensure access to comfortable and quality health services;
- attract new medical technology in the medical sphere;
- satisfy the medical needs of the public;
- providing medical services nationwide (1).

The level of economic development in the country is determined not only by the provision of medical services (how and how much health care can provide) but also it is fixed by the demand for these services and the opportunity to be satisfied. The demand of the population for medical services has been rising dramatically because of the changes in that sector for last years. The following figure shows the data on the health services provided by regions at the end of 2016 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Information on the quantity of health services provided by regions at the end of 2016 (www.stat.uz)

We know that the recent changes of the health of population are based on a number of factors such as the condition of living and lifestyle, the estate of the environment, the effectiveness and quality of health services, and the economies of economically developed and developing countries need to use medical services in the context of scientific and technical development (2). Consequently, the state focuses on the provision of equality of health services by taking into account the close link between the public's good quality of life and personal income needs. Recent years, control over the status of paid and free healthcare services in the country and their provision of state-run medical institutions has been reflected in the Decree "On the protection of the health of citizens" (3). In 1998, 10th of November identifies the categories of beneficiaries who get advantage from free medical services were identified in the Public Health Reform State Program. It is provided on the basis of the appropriate decision of the Cabinet of Ministers in free outpatient conditions (4). According to this, Infectious diseases, HIV disease, endocrinology diseases can be used by medical services the patients with oncology, tuberculosis, psychotropic and narcotic specialized hospitals. Free of charge medical care in inpatient conditions; disabled children, 2-3-invalids of the group, orphans, veterans of the war of 1941-1945 and equated to them, single pensioners, participants of the front labor front of 1941-1945, members of the Chernobyl NPP Victims teenagers aged under 17, military service soldiers 18-27 years of age can use this. In addition to those, the state guarantees health care services, as well as the privileges for issuing special permits from regional health departments. The State Program on Sanitary-Epidemiological Well-being of the Population of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2014-2018, "On the Prophylaxis of Iodine Deficiency Diseases", "On the State Program on the Strengthening of Reproductive Health of the Population of Uzbekistan for the Health of Mothers, Children and Adolescents" was adopted by the decree of 2221. According to the decree, it emphasis the introduction of gradual investment programs in the market of medical services in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2014-2018 and consistent and effective organization of the population's medical services. In order to improve the quality of medical services provided by the state, on April 1, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev made a decision "On measures to further develop the private sector, in the healthcare sector" with his decree of PP-2863. It is in line with this Decree to promote the development of the market for medical services, assist to support private sector, to solve issues that hinder the development of private health care facilities, provide with high-tech, medical equipment, specialized equipment and other equipment that would allow modern medical care to be provided to healthcare facilities, attracting access to private healthcare facilities in favorable credit and leasing mechanisms, encouraging active foreign investment in private healthcare, introduction of a system of medical insurance in the country, by taking into account the state of free medical care for the population and providing high-quality and inexpensive medical advice, as well as the provision of effective medical care through the organization of treatment, to develop the market of paid medical services in the country rapidly, and the involvement of qualified personnel in the medical field (5).

Additionally, in recent years, to double the number of private healthcare facilities by the factor of 2 the healthcare sector, the number of medical services provided and their quality improvement has been viewed as the result of government-provided benefits. Take into account the full utilization of the health care services of all categories of society this decision is particularly important in the development of private medical care in rural areas and the provision of certain benefits. It is signed with the development of the infrastructure of the public health services market in the countryside, strengthening its material and technical basis, as well as providing credit and financial assistance to the rural population (6). This decision was made by the private sector with the expansion of the range of services provided, only 177 types of medical services have been

permitted in the country's private healthcare facility, with only 50 permissible and nowadays practically all types of health care services are permitted. The type of permitted medical services is in high demand in the medical field for the population. Privileges of private medicine are illustrated in the following diagram (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Privileges of private medicine (www.stat.uz)

It was determined that by attracting foreign specialists in the sphere of private medicine, the income earned as a result of labour activity will be exempt from income tax and individual social payments. This Decree envisages release of private healthcare providers from several payments January 1, 2022 (www.stat.uz). For example, new micro-firms and small businesses, which provide medical services in rural areas, are exempt from single tax for a period of 10 years, which provides for the provision of high-quality and high-quality medical services in the country. All of the above-mentioned legislation, as well as improving the quality and effectiveness of medical services for the radical improvement of the well-being of the population, provide access to health care consumers to the formation and satisfaction of demand for this service. The organization and management of the

market of medical services in the Republic of Uzbekistan based on international standards explain that the sphere is rising to a new level.

Sources:

- (1). The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from February 7, 2017 "Strategy of Actions on the Five Priorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021", PD-4947
- (2). The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On citizens' health protection". Bulletin of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1996, No. 9
- (3). The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from November 10, 1998 of N UP-2107 "About State program of reforming of the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
- (4). On April 1, 2017 by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev "About measures for further development of the private sector in the sphere of healthcare" DP-2863
- (5). Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Collection of the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2007, No. 40, Art. 411.
- (6). The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 26, 2003 No UP-3214 "On Measures for Further Reforming the Health Care System".

References:

1. Rakhmonov, D. A. (2013). Advanced Financing Methods. Market, Money and Credit, (2). 64-67.

Список литературы:

1. Рахмонов Д. А. Расширенные методы финансирования // Рынок, деньги и кредит. 2013. № 2. С. 64-67.

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